

Influence of Examination Malpractice on Educational Management Undergraduate Students' Reading Culture in Rivers State Owned Universities in Rivers State

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Abstract

The research studies investigated influence of examination malpractice on Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned University in Rivers State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 398 Department of Educational Management students. The sample size of the study was 398. The sample size was taken as census. The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaires titled, Influence of Examination Malpractice on Students Reading Culture Questionnaire. The instrument used for data collection was face and content validated by an expert from Educational Management and two other experts from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation of the Faculty of Education in Rivers State University. The average reliability coefficient of the instruments was 0.81 which indicates a reasonable reliability coefficient. 398 copies of the instrument were administered directly to the respondents by the researchers and their two trained assistants and only 394 were retrieved amounting to 0.99 percent return of the administered instrument. The research questions posed were answered using mean and standard deviation while z-test was used to test the formulated hypotheses. Findings of the study revealed that, during and post examination malpractice to a high extent influence students' reading culture in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The researcher made the following recommendations that, there should be effective mechanisms put in place to curb and sanction students who engage in pre and during examination malpractices and concerted efforts should be made at improving the level of discipline meted out on teachers who award unmerited marks to students and the recipients of underserving marks.

Keywords: *Influence, Examination Malpractices, Students Reading Culture, Senior Secondary Schools.*

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Introduction

Examination in the school setting is the assessment of an examinee's ability, performance or achievement in a given task or subject matter. It is made up of a set of tasks, questions, situations etcetera. Intended to elicit particular types of behaviour from the examinee and can take different forms depending on the purpose. Generally, examination assesses an examinee's performance when he is confronted with series of questions, problems, tasks or situations set for him in order

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to ascertain the amount of knowledge that he has acquired, the extent to which he is able to utilize it or the quality and effectiveness of the skills he has developed Asuru in (Elenwo & Nwanguma, 2023). The result of such examination represents an estimate of the testee's behaviour (achievement, ability, performance, etcetera). Over the years, examination has become the basic characteristics of the school system all over the world. It is regarded as a requirement upon which the most important decisions about the progress of the learners and the performance of the teachers, school administrators and all stakeholders in the educational system are based (Agbor, 2013). Generally, the basic role of examination is to generate idea for promotion, certification, selection, prediction, monitoring of educational standards and performance, instructional and motivational aids, and research, (Asuru, 2012).

According to Akanni and Odojin (2015) examination malpractice that the prefix 'mal' is derived from a Latin abbreviation meaning bad. Examination malpractice therefore literally means bad practice applied in an examination in order to make the examinee earn an unmerited grade. It may be defined as an illegal act by the examination with the intent to make the examinee have an undue advantage or earn an unmerited grade (Aina, Okusana, Taiwo & Ogundepe, 2014). Section 19 of act 33, 1999 (Examination Malpractices Act 1999) in Anzene (2014) defines examination malpractice as an act, which constitutes an offence under the Degree (Act). Examination malpractice on the other hand was defined by West Africa Examination Council in Jimoh (2019) as any irregular behaviour exhibited by candidates or anybody charged with the responsibility of conducting examination in or outside the examination hall before, during or after such examination. Such acts include cheating at examination, stealing of question papers, disorderliness, obstruction, forgery, breach of duty, conspiracy, aiding, abetting and impersonation. It will also amount to examination malpractice where the examiner acts mala fide (in bad faith) by making the examinee be disadvantaged by awarding him a grade lower than he should have objectively earned (Anyanniyi & Anya, 2017). There are three forms of examination malpractice namely pre, during and post examination malpractice.

Asuru (2012) averred that, pre-examination malpractice is the type of malpractice students indulge in before the main examination. For example, paper leakage and buying of question paper before the examination. On the other hand, during examination malpractice as the name implies are malpractices perpetrated by students during examination. During examination malpractice takes the form of special centers, necking / giraffing / dubbing / alliance / ecomog, impersonation/mercenary, body writing or tattoo, collective settlement and so on and post examination malpractice are engaged in after the main examination such as, rewriting of the paper after examination, back for bed, cash and carry, altering scores and so forth. Studies on the examination malpractice exist in literature: pre, during and post examination malpractice (Agbo, 2023); (Mahashawari, 2015); (Udom, 2018) and (Onyebe, Uma & Emmanuel 2015). It is opined that, examination malpractice has continued unabated and has become sophisticated, complex and multidimensional and has destroyed the reading culture of the students who presently, sees examination malpractice as a short cut to passing the examinations.

Reading culture is a lifelong non-stop and steady routine. It denotes the student's behavior which articulates the likeness for reading and clarifies the essence and fondness for reading as well as rate of reading. Consequently, students' reading cultures hinge on the essence of reading which must not necessarily be for passing examinations alone but for acquisition of information, self-development, improvement of general knowledge, leisure, aesthetic need and entertainment (Adeniji, 2016). Ajumobi (2017) stressed positive reading culture as a requirement for a vigorous intellectual development that plays a very critical role in facilitating student's accomplishment of practical competence. Reading culture is an obsession to read with attestable, beneficial outcomes on addicts. It encompasses the gaining of positive attitude among students and this is vital to students' academic achievement. Reading culture of senior secondary school students is

disastrously lacking, Ailakhu and Nnegbu (2017) opined that reading as a culture, has declined over the past years and students are found wanting in the area of reading daily newspapers, magazines, let alone novels or literature books and this has resulted in poor acquisition of reading skills, good reading culture. Arising from the above, students had no other option but perpetually resorted to examination malpractice (Udoh, 2014). Akaranga and Ongong (2013) opined that reading culture has disappeared among students. They only rely on pre and during examination malpractice to pass their examinations. According to him, students have lost interest in reading due to their over-reliance in cheating in the examination hall, they want to cheat to be promoted to the next class.

Statement of the Problem

Examination malpractice in the educational system is widely discussed as cankerworm that poses a threat to authenticity of educational qualification (Udom 2018). It is a major challenge to examination bodies, government of Nigeria, school administrators and parents. A number of efforts have been made by government, schools examination bodies, concerned citizens to check the problem of examination. The effort examination malpractice made include expulsion of offenders from school, sanctioning of schools, supervisors and teachers and other individuals that aid and abate the conduct, enactment of laws, decrees and policies to check the act and establishment of examination ethics project. Other measures taken are conduct of public awareness campaign, integrity training, introduction of examination, ensuring proper spacing, good supervision during examination, embossment of photograph on all credentials (Petters & Okon, 2014). Unfortunately, these and other measures seem to have no effect the menace is still on the increase. Could this in any way influenced the reading culture of the students?

This research examined influence of examination malpractice on Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State University in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of examination malpractice on Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State University in Rivers State.

The study sought to achieve the following objectives;

1. Assess the extent during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.
2. examine the extent post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned Universities in Rivers State.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.

Methodology

The design of the study is the descriptive survey research design. Ayo (2013) opined that; it was necessary to use this design because it helped to determine the influence of one variable of the study on the other. That is to say that, it determined the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. This study was carried out in the two state owned universities in Rivers State. The population of this study consists of all the 398 levels 100 to 400 undergraduate students in the Department of Educational Management students in both schools. The sample size is 398. All the 398 students were taken as census. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled, Influence of Examination Malpractice on Students Reading Culture Questionnaire (IEMSRC). The questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A which focused on bio-data of the respondents, sought information on the personal background of the respondents while section B contains 10 items which were used to elicit responses of the respondents about the research questions using a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with assigned values of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The instrument used for data collection was face and content validated two other experts from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation and an expert in Department of Educational Management of the Faculty of Education in Rivers State University. The purpose of the study and the research questions were also made available to them at the time of validation. The corrections made by these three experts were incorporated in the final production of the instrument. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was carried out by the researcher. The Cronbach Alpha method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 20 students outside the selected Local Government Areas. The scores collated were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistics and the reliability coefficient are 0.84 and 0.78 for clusters 1-2 respectively. This proves that the instrument is reliable. 398 copies of the questionnaire were administered on the respondents directly by the researchers and their two trained research assistants for quick administration and retrieval. This was to ensure a high return rate of the instrument. The research assistants were trained to be polite to the respondents, to guide them on how to complete the questionnaire when asked and to assure them of their confidentiality. This was to ensure candid responses. In all, 394 copies of the 398 instrument sent out were retrieved; 203 from the females and 191 from the males, which amounts to 0.99 percent return rate. 4 copies of the instrument belonging to the male respondents were damaged. It took the researcher and her trained assistants three weeks to complete the exercise. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation. The Mean was used to answer the research questions using real limits to evaluate each item on the instrument. To test the significance of the two null hypotheses formulated for this study at 0.05, z-test was used. To determine the extent of any item in the questionnaire, a decision rule based on the real limits of numbers was used as follows for 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively: 3.50-4.0 (VHE), 2.50-3.49 (HE), 1.50-2.49 (LE) and 0.50-1.49 (VLE). The formulated null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated z value is greater than or equals to the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at .05 level of significance and failed to reject null hypotheses when the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at .05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.?

Table 1. Mean Responses of Female and Male Students on the Extent During Examination Malpractice Influence their Reading Culture

S/No	ITEMS	Female		Decisions	Males		Decisions
		— X	SD		— X	SD	
1	Leakage of examination paper reduces the urge to read	2.72	0.85	HE	3.30	1.05	HE
2	Purchasing of question papers before examination makes students not to read	2.53	0.72	HE	2.68	0.97	HE
3	Hiring of mercenaries reduces interest in reading	3.12	0.82	HE	2.70	0.93	HE
4	Usage of special centers discourages reading	3.25	0.76	HE	2.71	0.98	HE
5	Students who dub find it difficult to read	3.22	0.82	HE	2.69	0.95	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	2.97	0.79	HE	2.82	0.98	HE

Table 1 above showed that students reading culture was influenced by during examination malpractice to a high extent with the following mean values for items (1-5) for females: 2.72, 2.53, 3.12, 3.25 and 3.22 and for males: 3.30, 2.68, 2.70, 2.71 and 2.69 respectively. The standard deviation values range from 0.72 to 0.85 for females and 0.93 to 1.05, indicating a close response from respondents on all items.

Research Question 2

To what extent does post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owner universities in Rivers State?

Table 2. Mean Responses of Female and Male Students on the Extent Post Examination Malpractice Influence their Reading Culture

S/No	ITEMS	Female		Decisions	Males		Decisions
		— X	SD		— X	SD	
6	Paying to rewrite examinations makes students not to read	2.87	0.91	HE	2.61	0.98	HE
7	Sorting of teachers discourages reading amongst students	2.99	0.75	HE	2.63	0.94	HE
8	Altering of marks by teachers encourages students not to read	3.02	0.73	HE	2.88	1.04	HE
9	Paying to earn marks reduces the zeal to read	3.13	1.09	HE	2.69	0.95	HE
10	Students who sleep with teachers for marks do not read	3.11	1.05	HE	2.93	1.06	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.02	0.91	HE	2.75	0.99	HE

Table 2 above showed that students reading culture was influenced by post examination malpractice to a high extent with the following mean values for items (6-10) for females: 2.87, 2.99, 3.02, 3.13 and 3.11 and for males: 2.61, 2.61, 2.88, 2.69 and 2.93 respectively. The standard deviation values range from 0.73 to 1.09 for females and 0.94 to 1.06, indicating a close response from respondents on all items.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owner universities in Rivers State.

Table 3. Z-Test Analysis of the Responses on the Influence of During Examination on Educational Management Undergraduate Students' Reading Culture in Rivers State Owned Universities in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Females	203	2.97	0.79	392	.05	1.50	± 1.96	Failed to reject no significant difference
Males	191	2.82	0.81					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2022.

Table 3 above shows no significant difference in the mean responses of females and males on the extent to which during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. The z-calculated value of 1.50 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($1.50 \leq \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 392 at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.

Table 4. Z-Test Analysis of the Responses on the Influence of Post Examination Malpractice on Educational Management Undergraduate Students' Reading Culture in Rivers State Owned Universities in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Females	203	3.02	0.91	392	.05	2.70	± 1.96	Rejected no significant difference
Males	191	2.75	0.99					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2022.

Table 4 above shows significant difference in the mean responses of females and males on the extent to which post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. The z-calculated value of 2.70 was greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($2.70 \geq \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 392

at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings to research question 1 which focused on the extent to which during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. with grand mean scores of 2.97 for females and 2.82 for males revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, leakage of examination paper reduces the urge to read; purchasing of question papers before examination makes students not to read; hiring of mercenaries reduces interest in reading; usage of special centers discourages reading and students who dub find it difficult to read. So, the study revealed that during examination malpractice to a high extent influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. The finding was in agreement with the finding of Agbor (2013) that, poor reading culture, lack of adequate preparation for examination, non-seriousness on the part of students and too much stress on certificate acquisition make students to bribe their way through during examination.

Result on hypothesis 1 proved that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent to which during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. This indicated that the respondents; males and females, agreed to the fact that during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. This is in tandem with Maheshawari, (2015) who acknowledged that teachers make their question papers available for their friends, clients and relative to aid during examination malpractice.

The findings to research question 2 which focused on the extent to which post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. with grand mean scores of 3.02 for females and 2.75 for males revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, paying to rewrite examinations makes students not to read; sorting of teachers discourages reading amongst students; altering of marks by teachers encourages students not to read; paying to earn marks reduces the zeal to read and students who sleep with teachers for marks do not read. Thus, the study revealed that post examination malpractice to a high extent influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. The finding was in agreement with the finding of Udom (2018), which revealed that students' actual level of cheating after examination is significantly dependent on the level of their attitude toward reading.

Result on hypothesis 2 proved that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the extent to which post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. This indicated that the respondents; males and females, disagreed to the fact that post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State. This is in consonance with Onyibe, Uma and Emmanuel (2015) who opined that with examination malpractice students will focus more on cheating than reading.

Conclusion

It was concluded that students in senior secondary schools engage in pre, during and post examination malpractice which contributes to poor reading culture amongst them. Also, there was no significant difference in mean scores of both the males and females as regards the extent pre and during examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned universities in Rivers State and a significance difference in mean scores of both the males and females as regards the extent post examination malpractice influence Educational Management undergraduate students' reading culture in Rivers State owned university in Rivers State.

Recommendations

1. There should be effective mechanisms put in place to curb and sanction students who engage in pre and during examination malpractices.
2. Concerted efforts should be made at improving the level of discipline meted out on teachers who award unmerited marks to students and the recipients of underserving marks.

References

- Adeniji, M. A. (2016). Use of school library by teachers in Ogun State. *Nigerian Library Journal*, 5(2), 35-42.
- Agbo, B. (2013). Library Reading Culture and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Osun State. *Middle Belt Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6(2), 42-58.
- Agbor, O. (2013). *Psycho-social variables and examination malpractice among primary school pupils in Delta State, Nigeria*. Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation. Delta State University, Delta State.
- Ailakhu, U. V. & Unegbu, V. E. (2017). Libraries' promotion of reading culture and student's responsiveness in selected secondary schools in Lagos State. *Library and Information Science*, 4(1), 30-42.
- Aina, A. J., Okusaga, T. O., Taiwo, A. & Ogundipe, T. C. (2014). The role of library in promoting reading habits among Nigerians. *Journal of research in Education and society*, 2(1), 168-179.
- Ajumobi, C. J. (2017). *Reading as a catalyst*. Owerri: TJN Publishers.
- Akanni, O. O. & Odofin, B. (2015). Reducing examination malpractices in Nigerian schools through effective continuous assessment techniques as an alternative to one-shot examination in Osun State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2(1), 91 – 101. <https://doi.org/10.12691/EDUCATION-3-6-18>
- Akaranga, S. I. & Ongong, J. J. (2013). The phenomenon of examination malpractice: An example of Nairobi and Kenyatta Universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(18), 87 – 96.
- Anzene, S. J. (2014). Trends in examination malpractice in Nigerian educational system and its effects on the socio-economic development of Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3): 1 – 8.
- Asuru, V. A. (2012). *Examination malpractice: Agenda for a change*. Owas Haven Enterprises.
- Ayanniyi, B. A. & Anya, C. O. (2017). Forms and consequences of examination malpractice in Nigerian schools and Universities: What should the stakeholders do? *International journal of education, training and learning*, 1(1), 9-21. <http://dx.doi.org/10.33094/6.2017.11.9.21>

- Ayo, S. (2013). *Fundamentals of test and measurement in education*. Calabar University of Calabar Press.
- Elenwo, P. M. & Nwanguma, T. K. (2023). Electronic invigilation inclusion in curbing examination malpractices among postgraduate students in selected public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*, 6(2), 100-113. <http://dx.doi.org/10.52589/BJELDP-Y5JNZPPC>
- Jimoh, B. O. (2019). Examination malpractice in secondary schools in Nigeria: What sustains it? *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 1(3), 101 – 108.
- Maheshwari, V. K. (2015). *Malpractices in examinations. The termites destroying the educational set up*. Rookee, India: K.L.D.A. (P.G) College.
- Onyibe, C. O., Uma, U. U. & Emmanuel, I. (2015). Examination malpractice in Nigeria: Causes and effects on national development. *Journal of education and practice*, 6(26), 125- 134.
- Petters, J. S., & Okon, O. (2014). Students' perception of causes and effects of examination malpractice in the Nigerian educational system: The way forward for quality education. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(14), 125-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.671>
- Udom, N. S. (2018). *Factors that affect students' tendency to cheat in examination*. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, University of Calabar, Calabar Nigeria.

